

PSYCHOLINGUISTICS AND PERSONAL VALUE ORIENTATIONS

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Abstract. *Within the framework of the cultural direction in psycholinguistics, there are works devoted to intercultural communication. Intercultural communication is the communication of representatives of different nations among themselves, implying the exchange of value preferences and orientations.*

Keywords: *Psycholinguistics, intercultural communication, value orientations.*

ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИКА И ЛИЧНОСТНЫЕ ЦЕННОСТНЫЕ ОРИЕНТАЦИИ

Аннотация. *В рамках культурологического направления в психолингвистике имеются работы, посвященные межкультурной коммуникации. Межкультурная коммуникация – это общение представителей разных народов между собой, подразумевающее обмен ценностными предпочтениями и ориентациями.*

Ключевые слова: *Психолингвистика, межкультурная коммуникация, ценностные ориентации.*

Psycholinguistics, intercultural communication, value orientations. There are a large number of philosophical concepts of "man". In sociology and psychology, there are no fewer than a number of different points of view on "man" and attempts to describe in more or less detail various properties and qualities of him. All this knowledge cannot satisfy pedagogy and, when correlated with each other, cannot withstand mutual criticism. The analysis and classification of these concepts and points of view, as well as an explanation of why they do not and cannot provide knowledge that satisfies pedagogy, is a matter of special and very extensive research. An object of science is a collection of individual objects that it studies. The subject of science is an abstract system of objects or a system of abstract objects.

The subject of linguistics is the system of linguistic means used in communication. The subject of psycholinguistics is different from that of linguistics. She does not consider the structure of the sign system, but the process of creating and perceiving language signs in the minds of their native speakers. Psycholinguistics coincides with linguistics in terms of object, and in terms of subject and methods - with psychology, which studies the generation, functioning and structure of the mental reflection of reality. Even within the framework of psycholinguistics, there are different approaches to speech activity. Thus, N. Chomsky's transformational generative grammar (3) assumes that a person builds speech according to the rules of combinatorics. Within the framework of behaviorism, speech is analyzed in the "stimulus-response" paradigm. The theory of activity comes from the speaker's activity. No model is complete and does not exhaust all the properties of an object.

There are several definitions of psycholinguistics. One of them is this: psycholinguistics is a science that studies the processes of speech formation, as well as the perception and formation of speech in their correlation with the language system (1). This definition notes that psycholinguistics has three subject areas:

1) speech production (in an individual speech act);

2) speech perception (in an individual speech act);

3) the formation of speech (in the process of becoming a child's personality). And in each case, it is assumed that psycholinguistics addresses those aspects of these types of speech activity that are conditioned by the language system Charles Osgood gave a different definition: "Psycholinguistics studies those processes in which the intentions of speakers are transformed into signals of the code accepted in a given culture and these signals are transformed into interpretations of listeners" (4). In other words, psycholinguistics deals with the processes of encoding and decoding, since they correlate the state of messages with the state of communication participants.

With this approach, the subject of psycholinguistics can be the processes of speech production and perception in their correlation with the physiological and mental state of communication participants. Here, the processes of speech correlate not with the language system, but with a person, with his psyche. Since currently both of these approaches seem to coexist, AL.

Leontiev offers a compromise definition of this discipline. The subject of psycholinguistics, in his opinion, is the relationship of personality with the structure and functions of speech activity, on the one hand, and language as the main component of the image of the human world, on the other (2). Within the framework of psycholinguistics, there are studies focused on the philosophical aspects of linguistics and psychology. These include works on the problems of the interaction of language and thinking; language and consciousness; on the problems of the formation of human consciousness in ontogenesis and phylogeny (the Paryuk Society in 1865 banned the consideration of any hypotheses about the origin of language as "useless" and "unproductive"); in general, the problems of sign thinking. There are a number of problems in psycholinguistics affecting areas related to cultural studies and national psychology. In particular, the general position is that the discrepancies in the linguistic worldview are due not only to the structure of the language, but also to the different vision of the world by native speakers of this language. The national and cultural peculiarities of communication are manifested in at least two aspects. This is, firstly, the relationship of language, thinking, memory, communication, and in general, the place of language in different types of human activity. Secondly, these are processes and means of communication that have national specifics.

At the junction of psycholinguistics and ethnopsychology is the problem of studying the speech behavior of different peoples. In particular, observations show that northern peoples - for example, Norwegians, Swedes, Finns - speak more quietly and less emotionally than southern ones - in particular, Spaniards and Italians. Many southern peoples - Georgians, Gypsies, Turks, Arabs, tall ethnic groups of the black race - for the most part speak louder than Italians and Spaniards.

Some Oriental peoples - Japanese, Vietnamese, Burmese, Hindus - communicate quietly.

Here, probably, along with other factors, the place of residence and the associated climatic conditions play an important role. However, in terms of loudness, the neighboring peoples living in the same geographical latitude speak differently - the Germans, the French, the British. Within the framework of the cultural direction in psycholinguistics, there are works devoted to intercultural communication. Intercultural communication is the communication of representatives of different nations among themselves. An example of such research may be work on the study of how the recipient of one culture understands texts created within another culture. Such texts can

be called foreign cultural texts. Value-oriented activity is not an external assessment, preference and choice of ready-made values-and the very process of their formation in the structure of the object, External evaluative activity is, of course, included as an auxiliary in this independent creative process of creating values, or, more precisely, recreating over and over again by each person, each generation, its hierarchy of universal and spiritual values and their corresponding levels of culture. This spontaneous, but ultimately conscious process of changing value priorities is the internal mechanism of revaluation of values. Values, as we have seen, cannot be imposed and taken away by force or cunning, they cannot be bought, sold or even presented ready-made.

You can't enter them like a new apartment, put on them like a new suit, use them like bread and water. It is impossible to simply join values, they need to be created independently, created in themselves and recreated every time in every value situation anew, overcoming the alienation of weakness, cowardice and disbelief. The values of love, faith and courage, goodness and justice function only in the process of their independent and free creation by man and society.

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